

1 **CDKN3 inactivation compensates for ERBB2 inhibition and is associated with trastuzumab**
2 **resistance.**

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8 Treatment failure in patients with HER2+ breast cancer is associated with progression to CNS
9 metastasis. We recently defined CDK10 activation as a compensatory mechanism following HER2
10 chemical (pharmacologic) inhibition in humans with HER2+ breast cancer, and demonstrated separately
11 that quantitative determination of differential expression was sufficient for identification of synthetic lethality
12 and kinase addiction. We demonstrate here from study of RNA-sequencing measurement of total
13 transcription following pharmacologic inhibition of ERBB2 with two separate HER2 kinase inhibitors in
14 human cancer cells *in vitro* that the cell cycle inhibitor CDKN3 is compensatorily silenced in response to
15 ERBB2 inhibition. Accordingly, CDKN3 repression was observed *in vivo* in HER2+ breast cancer patients
16 who failed treatment with trastuzumab (resistance). CDKN3 silencing compensates for ERBB2 inhibition.
17 We argue CDKN activation is a viable option for reversal or prevention of resistance to trastuzumab.
18 CDKN repression appears to be a central mechanism by which cancer cells evade cell cycle restriction.
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Results

We studied total transcription in human cancer cells treated with small molecule inhibitors of the kinase encoded by *ERBB2*, HER2, to identify kinases activated by the cancer cell to compensate for HER2 kinase inhibition.

Figure 1: Treatment of prostate cancer cells with the first generation HER2 inhibitor lapatinib results in compensatory repression of CDKN3.

GSE199800

n=6 DU145 (control: *n*=3 untreated and *n*=3 DMSO treated)
n=2 DU145 treated with lapatinib

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1033	5.86E-02	0.446	1.891295	0.8437886	251.97	CDKN3	1743/11449	

Figure 2: Treatment of breast cancer cells with the second generation HER2 inhibitor neratinib results in compensatory repression of CDKN3.

GSE249573

n=4 MDA-MB-453 and HCC1954 (*n*=2 each; control; DMSO treated)
n=4 MDA-MB-453 and HCC1954 (*n*=2 each; control; neratinib treated)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1033	4.55E-05	0.1869	4.0777791	0.7620432	1403.14	CDKN3	159/19129	

Pharmacologic inhibition of the HER2 kinase in cancer cells resulted in repression (silencing) of CDKN3 (Figure 1 and 2). Next, we measured total transcription *in vivo* in HER2+ breast cancer patients who had developed resistance to treatment with the HER2+ monoclonal antibody trastuzumab (Figure 3).

Figure 3: CDKN3 is silenced *in vivo* in HER2+ patients who have developed resistance to trastuzumab.

GSE162187

n=2 primary tumors from humans with HER2+ breast cancer treated with trastuzumab; treatment sensitive
n=4 primary tumors from humans with HER2+ breast cancer treated with trastuzumab; treatment resistant

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1033	1.59E-02	0.505	2.4110228	1.2172865	109.42	CDKN3	554/19507	

Discussion

We demonstrated here through measurement of total transcription in cancer cells treated with small molecule inhibitors of the HER2 kinase lapatinib and neratinib that CDKN3 is compensatorily silenced in response to HER2 inhibition. Consistent with CDKN3 repression in response to pharmacologic inhibition of HER2, we found CDKN3 silencing in the tumors of patients with HER2+ breast cancer that had developed resistance to the HER2-targeted monoclonal antibody trastuzumab.

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We recently described CDK10 activation as a general mechanism to HER2 inhibition. Co-administration of a CDK10 inhibitor with senescence-inducing CDK4/6 inhibitors (manuscript in preparation) that target senescence-associated *CDKN* expression as a general mechanism by which cancer cells resist treatment with chemotherapy (manuscript in preparation), together with a CDKN activator (we consider CDK4/6 inhibitors, as senescence inducing agents, to be CDKN activators) is a viable strategy to counteract resistance to trastuzumab.